

TAXATION OF LABOR AND CAPITAL INCOME IN TURKEY AND AZERBAIJAN: A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE TAX BURDEN

Jafarova R.

Türkiye, Anadolu University
ORCID: 0009-0008-3233-1222

Erkan Üyümez M.

Prof. Dr.
Türkiye, Anadolu University
ORCID: 0000-0001-7567-3486

ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to comparatively examine the tax burden on labor and capital income in Turkey and Azerbaijan and to reveal the key trends in this area. Within the scope of labor income, wage earners are particularly considered. The primary reason for this is that wage incomes are largely taxed through source-based withholding, and the tax burden is concentrated directly and regularly on this segment of the population.

Capital income, on the other hand, refers to the earnings individuals derive from their assets, and its taxation structure exhibits a more distinct and flexible framework compared to labor income. These incomes are taxed through various methods, and different rates and mechanisms may apply in practice. This situation makes it difficult to determine the tax burden on capital income in a direct and clear manner.

When evaluated overall, there are structural differences between the taxation of labor and capital income, and these differences directly affect the distribution of the tax burden. The study analyzes the tax burden on labor and capital income in Turkey and Azerbaijan and discusses the findings in comparison with OECD data.

Keywords: tax burden, labor income, capital income, Turkey, Azerbaijan.

1. Introduction

The expansion of public authority's activities in the economic and social spheres naturally entails a greater need for financing. The most important tool for meeting this need is taxes, and the taxation process imposes both financial and perceptual burdens on individuals and institutions. While tax payments reduce taxpayers' disposable income, they also exert a psychological impact due to the sense of obligation.

The concept of tax burden is considered one of the key indicators showing what proportion of income generated in an economy is transferred to the public sector. In this respect, it reveals not only the size of public finance but also how taxation is distributed among different segments of society. The distribution of the tax burden provides an important metric for assessing whether the fiscal system operates fairly. (OECD, 2025; Çevik, 2005). The findings of this study are consistent with D. Pashayeva's view that improving tax administration and tax control mechanisms plays an important role in strengthening the effectiveness of the tax system (D. Pashayeva, 2019). Today, how the tax burden is shared among individuals, sectors, and income groups is increasingly being debated. (Karaş & Hayrulloğlu, 2023). In this context, the tax burden is directly related to macro objectives such as economic balance, income distribution, and sustainable growth, beyond being merely a financial indicator. It also enables comparisons between different countries and economic structures. When examining the taxation of wage income, significant differences can emerge among various groups due to different practices (Öztürk & Ozansoy, 2011; Giray, 2018). It is observed that the tax burden is not distributed equally, particularly among public and private sector employees or between individuals with different statuses within the public sector. These disparities are among the elements that

strengthen discussions regarding the fairness dimension of the tax system.

2. Overview of capital and labor incomes in Turkey and Azerbaijan

The tax-related evaluation of income elements constitutes an important area of study in understanding the functioning of financial systems. In particular, the methods used in taxing earnings derived from labor and capital reflect states' economic priorities and fiscal policy choices. Although these two types of income are covered under the same income tax framework in tax legislation, the methods applied to them often rely on different techniques.

The regular and trackable nature of earnings derived from labor places these incomes within a more standardized tax structure. In contrast, the diversity of capital-derived income leads to the emergence of more flexible and differentiated tax regulations. In particular, special regulations for capital income are frequently employed to encourage investment, increase savings, and support economic growth.

In this context, the differences that emerge in tax systems shape not only collection methods but also the actual distribution of the tax burden across income groups. Demonstrating the tax policy differences between labor and capital is crucial for evaluating the economic and social impacts of countries' tax policies. In this section, the current taxation structure in Turkey and Azerbaijan will be examined separately in terms of labor and capital income.

2.1 Capital and labor incomes in Turkey

Taxes, which constitute the primary source of revenue for public finance, are generally designed taking into account taxpayers' ability to pay. Since income level is the most important indicator of ability to pay, taxes levied on income are at the center of modern tax systems. In this context, income tax includes both earnings derived from labor and returns from capital sources

within its tax base. However, there are certain economic and structural differences between different types of income. Income derived from work is considered "earned income" because it results directly from an individual's labor and effort. In contrast, capital income is regarded as a more passive form of earnings because it arises as a result of past savings or asset ownership. This distinction reinforces the view that the type of income should also be taken into account when measuring solvency. When examining the structure of tax systems, it is observed that there are significant methodological differences between the taxation methods for labor income and capital income. This difference arises not only from tax rates but also from collection timings and implementation mechanisms. While labor income is generally taxed through withholding at source on wages, capital income is subject to a declaration-based system with periodic collection. (Organ & Yavuz, 2017). The system applied to wage incomes constitutes a highly rapid and automated collection mechanism since the tax is deducted before income is received. This situation leads to laborers bearing the tax burden before they receive their income.

In Turkey, the taxation of capital income is addressed within the framework of securities and real estate capital gains under the Income Tax Law (Republic of Turkey, 1961; Nacar &

Karabacak, 2022). Securities income comprises interest on deposits, dividend income, repo earnings, and returns from various financial investment instruments, while real estate income consists of earnings resulting from the rental of immovable properties. The methods applied in taxing these types of income exhibit a more distinct and flexible structure compared to those applied to labor income.

The stop-loss system is predominantly employed in taxing securities income (OECD, 2025). In particular, withholding taxes levied at source on deposit interest and earnings from certain investment instruments facilitate tax collection. However, low-rate withholding taxes applied to certain income elements or specific declaration thresholds may reduce the effective tax burden on capital income. This situation is considered to be a result of fiscal policies aimed at encouraging investment instruments.

Regarding the taxation of real estate capital income, the exemption amounts granted to taxpayers and the possibilities for expense deductions draw attention. In particular, the actual expense and flat-rate expense methods enable the reduction of the taxable base arising from rental income. These practices have a mitigating effect on the effective tax burden faced by real estate owners.

Another noteworthy aspect in the taxation of capital income is that tax planning opportunities for this type of income are broader compared to labor income. The timing of income receipt, the nature of the investment instrument, and options for benefiting from tax advantages provide capital holders with a more flexible course of action. In contrast, the direct and regular withholding of tax at source on labor income greatly limits such flexibility.

Consequently, when the withholding tax practices, exemption regulations, and expense deduction opportunities in the taxation of capital income in Turkey are considered together, it becomes apparent that the tax burden on this type of income is more flexible and relatively manageable compared to labor income. This situation reveals a significant difference in terms of the distribution of the tax burden among different types of income.

2.2. Capital and labor income in Azerbaijan

The Azerbaijani tax system is based on a structure that applies both direct and indirect taxes and covers the incomes of both natural and legal persons. (Republic of Azerbaijan, 2000).

Since the taxation of labor and capital incomes is carried out through different mechanisms within this system, certain disparities arise in the distribution of the tax burden. Labor incomes are primarily subject to taxation under personal income tax, and a progressive tax structure is applied. While lower rates apply up to a certain income level, the tax rate increases as income rises (Akhundzada, 2020). This situation results in an increasing tax burden on labor income with rising income levels.

In Azerbaijan, the taxation of capital income is considered within the general income tax system under the umbrella of income from securities and real estate. Capital income consists of interest income, dividend income, returns from various financial investments, and income derived from the rental of real estate. The taxation structure exhibits a simpler and less differentiated appearance compared to Turkey.

The rates applied in the taxation of capital gains may vary depending on the type of income and relevant regulations. The taxation system applied to interest and dividend income generally has a simpler structure and features limited rate differences among different investment instruments. This situation enables tax practices to be conducted within a more predictable framework.

Regarding real estate capital income, rental income is declared within a specific legal framework and taxed according to general income tax principles. The absence of comprehensive exemption and expense deduction mechanisms as found in Turkey leads to a more direct approach to taxation. However, the system's simple structure enables taxpayers to more easily track their tax obligations.

The key feature that stands out in the taxation of capital income in the Azerbaijani tax system is that tax rates are relatively low and the implementation mechanisms are more integrated (Məmmədov, 2022; Hasanov, 2009). This structure contributes to keeping the overall tax burden on capital income at a more modest level compared to many developed economies. It is also considered an important fiscal policy tool in terms of supporting the investment environment and encouraging capital mobility.

As a result, the taxation of capital income in Azerbaijan presents a more integrated picture compared to Turkey due to its simple rate structure and more limited differentiations. The implemented system keeps the tax burden on capital income relatively low, presenting a more advantageous tax structure compared to labor income in this regard.

3. Tax burden on capital and labor income in Turkey and Azerbaijan

In the previous section, the structural framework regarding the taxation of labor and capital income in the tax systems of Turkey and Azerbaijan was outlined. However, evaluating taxation systems solely based on legal regulations is not sufficient. Examining the actual burden imposed by these regulations on income groups enables a more accurate analysis of the effectiveness and fairness dimensions of tax systems. In this context, the following section will discuss the tax burden on labor and capital income in greater detail for both countries.

3.1 The tax burden on labor income in Turkey

The taxation of labor income in tax systems entails certain limitations both in terms of the method of determining the tax base and the applied tax schedule. The expense items that can be taken into account in the calculation of taxable income for wage income are quite limited in scope. The fact that employees can deduct only limited items from their taxable income, such as mandatory social security deductions, insurance premiums within certain limits, and union dues, leads to the taxation of labor income based on a broad tax base. This

situation causes employees to face a higher taxable amount compared to their actual income.

Additionally, their labor income is often subject to a progressive tax rate. As income levels increase, the tax rate also rises, creating a progressively concentrated tax burden, particularly on wage earners. This structure can lead to a more limited than expected increase in net earnings with income growth. In particular, moving into different tax brackets throughout the year can lead to significant reductions in employees' net income.

Another noteworthy aspect in the taxation of labor income is that these incomes are largely taxed at source. Since wages are subject to tax deduction before being paid to employees, tax collection is instantaneous and certain. This ensures high efficiency in terms of tax compliance, but eliminates flexibility for employees. Consequently, when the limited deductions for expenses in the taxation of labor income, the progressive tax structure, and the source-based deduction method are considered together, it can be said that a concentrated and directly felt tax burden arises on this type of income. This structure creates a more pronounced pressure on labor income in terms of the distributional impact of the tax system.

Taxable monthly income	Tax rate
Up to 190,000 TL	15%
For the first 190,000 TL of 400,000 TL, 28,500 TL, and the excess amount	20%
70,500 TL for 400,000 TL of 1,000,000 TL, (in wage income 70,500 TL for 400,000 TL of 1,500,000 TL), the remainder	27%
232,500 TL for 1,000,000 TL of 5,300,000 TL, (in wage income 367,500 TL for 1,500,000 TL of 5,300,000 TL), the remainder	35%
1,737,500 TL for 5,300,000 TL more than 5,300,000 TL, (1,697,500 TL for 5,300,000 TL more than 5,300,000 TL in wage income), surplus	40%

Source: Income Tax Law Art. 103, current tariff for 2026 (Republic of Turkey, 1961).

3.2. Tax burden on capital income in Turkey

In Turkey, the tax burden on capital income varies depending on the type of income obtained, but it is predominantly applied through the withholding (source-based deduction) system.

Dividend income, which is considered a type of capital income, is generally subject to a 10% withholding tax; however, for natural persons, half of the dividend income is exempt from income tax, and the remaining portion must be included in the annual income tax return if it exceeds a certain threshold. This structure both partially reduces double taxation and enables more controlled taxation of investment income.

Regarding interest income, taxation rates vary depending on the type of investment instrument (PwC Worldwide Tax Summaries, 2025). While stopaj rates, which generally range from 5% to 15% depending on the term length for deposit interest, may periodically drop to 0% for certain public debt instruments such as government bonds and Treasury bills. Regarding income earned from investment funds, withholding tax is

generally applied at a rate between 0% and 10% depending on the type of fund, and in most cases no separate declaration obligation arises.

Overall, the tax system for capital income in Turkey is relatively low-burden and simple, with withholding tax rates ranging from 0% to 15% and limited reporting obligations. This structure aims to encourage the redirection of savings to financial markets while also increasing the attractiveness of the investment environment.

3.3. Tax burden on labor income in Azerbaijan

Within the Azerbaijani tax system, the taxation of wage income constitutes an important area directly affecting both employees in the labor market and their employers. The tax burden on labor income consists not only of income tax but also of various socially mandated deductions. In this context, wage income is subject to primarily income tax, mandatory social security contributions, unemployment insurance contributions, and mandatory health insurance payments. These deductions are generally calculated by the employer and transferred on behalf of the employee to the relevant

public institutions. This situation results in a large portion of wage income being taxed at source. In recent years, various structural reforms have been implemented in Azerbaijan to reduce the tax burden on labor income (Mammadov, 2022). To specifically encourage the non-oil private sector, reductions in income tax rates and facilitative regulations on certain social security contributions have been implemented. These reforms are linked to the goals of increasing employment and strengthening the formal wage structure. The taxation of wage incomes may vary depending on the sector and income level. While a lower-rate and progressive tax structure is applied in non-oil sectors, some sectors may be subject to more traditional rates. This situation indicates that the tax burden imposed on labor income is not homogeneous. In addition, mandatory contributions to social security and health systems are among the significant factors that increase the overall

tax burden on labor income. These deductions are borne by both employers and employees, thus imposing a dual burden on wage costs. Consequently, the taxation of labor income in Azerbaijan is not limited to income tax alone but has a multi-component structure that includes social contributions. Therefore, the total tax burden on wages can vary significantly depending on the structure of the system.

3.4 Personal income tax Rates (Personal income tax)

Taking into account the provisions of Article 101.1-1 of the tax code, the tax on the monthly income of individuals from Hired work is deducted according to the following table. This schedule applies only to those who are taxed on the monthly income of individuals working in the oil and gas sector and taxpayers belonging to the public sector.

Taxable monthly income	Tax rate
Up to 2,500 AZN	3%
From 2,500 AZN to 8,000 AZN	10% of the amount between 75 AZN + 2,500 AZN and 8,000 AZN.
Over 2,500 AZN	625 AZN + 14% of the amount exceeding 8,000 AZN.

The tax is deducted from the monthly income of individuals who do not have activities in the oil and gas

sector and work in taxpayers belonging to the non-public sector at the following rates.

Taxable monthly income	Tax rate
Up to 2,500 AZN	14%
Over 2,500 AZN	350 AZN + 25% of the amount exceeding 2,500 AZN.

Source: Tax Council Of Azerbaijan Republic, 2026

3.5 Tax burden on capital income in Azerbaijan

In Azerbaijan, taxation of capital income is considered within the general income tax system rather than as a separate and independent tax regime. Within this framework, capital income earned by natural persons is generally subject to income tax, with applicable rates typically starting at around 14% and potentially rising to 25% depending on income level and relevant regulations. For legal entities, capital income is considered within corporate earnings and is taxed at the standard corporate tax rate. This rate is generally applied at

approximately 20%. This structure demonstrates that instead of a single special regime for the taxation of capital income, an integrated approach within the general tax system is adopted. Overall, the tax burden on capital income in Azerbaijan is structured within a relatively simpler system, with taxation largely occurring at the time of income realization and based on general tax rates (PwC Worldwide Tax Summaries, 2025; Hasanov, 2009).

4. Comparison Comparison of Labor and Capital Income Taxation in Turkey and Azerbaijan

Table 1.

Comparison of Labor and Capital Income Taxation in Turkey and Azerbaijan

Criteria	Turkey (Labor)	Turkey (Capital)	Azerbaijan (Labor)	Azerbaijan (Capital)
Tax type	Income tax + SSI	Income + corporate tax	Income tax + social contributions	Income + corporate tax
Tax rate	15% – 40% (progressive)	5% – 40% (variable)	Non-oil private sector: 3%-10%, 14%(progressive) State & oil/gas sector: 14% – 25% (progressive)	14%- 25% (<i>Individuals</i>) ~20% (<i>Corporate entities</i>)
Taxation method	At source (withholding)	Withholding + declaration	At source	General system
Additional charges	SOCISO, unemployment premium	Generally none	Social insurance, health	Limited
Exception/advantage	Limited	Widespread	Limited	Moderate
Exception/advantage	High	Low-Medium	Medium-High	Moderate

Source: Prepared by the author using the Tax Codes of the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Republic of Turkey.

Although the tax systems of Turkey and Azerbaijan possess distinct structural features in terms of taxing labor and capital income, they produce similar results in terms of the resulting tax burden distribution. In both countries, labor income has a more regular, transparent, and source-based taxed structure, while capital income stands out as an area characterized by greater flexibility and taxation through different methods.

In Turkey, labor income faces a high and sustained tax burden due to the progressive tax schedule and mandatory social security deductions. Taxing wages at the source directly increases the efficiency of tax collection but severely limits tax planning opportunities for taxpayers. In contrast, capital income is subject to a more flexible taxation regime through varying taxation methods according to different income types, withholding tax practices, and various exemption arrangements. This situation can often result in the effective tax burden on capital income being below the statutory rates.

In Azerbaijan, the tax system exhibits a simpler and more integrated structure. Labor income is taxed at specific rates, and in addition, social security and health contributions increase the overall burden. Instead of forming a separate tax category, capital income is treated within the general income tax system. This structure offers a simpler and more predictable framework for taxation, but it also results in a more limited set of elements determining the tax burden on capital income.

When both countries are considered together, although the taxation methods differ, the resulting outcome is similar: capital income faces a lower or more manageable tax burden compared to labor income. This situation raises significant debates, particularly regarding the distribution of the tax burden and economic justice. As international studies have shown, the trend towards more favorable taxation of capital income is not unique to these two countries but is considered part of a broader systematic structure.

5. Capital Tax Burden Comparison in Turkey and Azerbaijan within the Framework of OECD Data

The taxation of capital income is carried out at lower rates and generally through a separate system, distinct from the taxation of labor income, in many countries. In OECD countries, these income types (dividends, interest, and other investment returns) are generally treated within the framework of a dual income tax approach, and the average tax burden varies between approximately 15% and 23%. In this context, although capital income enjoys more favorable tax regimes compared to labor income, there are significant differences across countries.

In Turkey, the taxation of capital income is largely carried out through the withholding tax mechanism. Generally, a 10% withholding tax is applied on dividend income, and if the income exceeds a certain threshold, half of the income may be subject to income tax. With regard to interest income, withholding tax rates ranging from 0% to 15% are applied depending on

the type of investment instrument. In certain public debt instruments, such as government bonds, the tax burden may periodically approach zero. This structure causes the effective tax burden on capital income in Turkey to remain at low levels in most cases, with the general range falling around 0%–15%.

In Azerbaijan, the taxation of capital income has a simpler structure. Dividend and interest income is generally subject to withholding taxes of around 5–10%, while capital income is largely treated within a flat-rate income tax system. Compared to Turkey, there are

fewer exceptions and a less tiered structure, which results in a simpler system but one that imposes a relatively more uniform tax burden.

When compared to OECD countries, Turkey's tax burden on capital income generally falls at the lower end of the average range, and in some cases, lower effective rates are observed (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, 2025). As for Azerbaijan, it exhibits a structure that is closer to the OECD average but with a more fixed rate.

Figure 1. Capital Income Tax Burden Comparison

Source: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, 2025

Overall, when evaluated, Turkey implements a low-rate system with a strong emphasis on incentives for capital income and with a focus on withholding taxes, while Azerbaijan adopts a simpler but relatively more standardized taxation approach.

6. Comparison of Labor Tax Burdens in Turkey

and Azerbaijan within the Framework of OECD Data

The data from Taxing Wages published by the OECD reveals that the tax wedge, which shows the total tax burden on labor income, exhibits significant differences between countries.

Table 2.

Comparison of total tax wedge, 2025
As % of labour costs

Country ¹	Total tax wedge 2025 (1)	Annual change, 2025/2024 (in percentage points) ²			
		Tax wedge (2)	Income tax (3)	Employee SSC (4)	Employer SSC ³ (5)
Belgium	52.5	0.08	-0.02	-0.01	0.11
Germany	49.3	1.34	0.28	0.53	0.52
France	47.2	0.06	0.06	0.00	0.00
Austria	47.1	0.29	-0.01	0.00	0.00
Italy	45.8	-1.21	-1.21	0.00	0.00
Slovenia	45.3	0.63	-0.06	0.32	0.37
Slovak Republic	42.7	0.20	0.20	0.00	0.00
Estonia	42.6	1.95	1.95	0.00	0.00
Finland	42.5	0.35	-0.09	0.09	0.35
Spain	41.4	0.31	0.25	0.00	0.05
Czechia	41.2	0.24	0.24	0.00	0.00
Hungary	41.2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Country ¹	Total tax wedge 2025 (1)	Annual change, 2025/2024 (in percentage points) ²			
		Tax wedge (2)	Income tax (3)	Employee SSC (4)	Employer SSC ³ (5)
Sweden	41.1	-0.37	-0.37	0.00	0.00
Türkiye	40.3	0.76	0.29	-0.08	0.55
Luxembourg	40.2	0.24	-0.54	-0.11	0.88
Latvia	40.1	-1.44	-1.44	0.00	0.00
Lithuania	39.8	0.38	0.38	0.00	0.00
Portugal	39.3	-0.24	-0.24	0.00	0.00
Greece	39.3	-0.16	0.54	-0.36	-0.34
Norway	36.4	-0.07	0.02	-0.09	0.00
Netherlands	35.9	0.04	0.23	-0.41	0.22
Denmark	35.8	-0.41	-0.48	0.00	0.06
Poland	35.0	0.28	0.32	0.01	-0.04
Japan	33.1	0.39	0.46	-0.04	-0.04
Ireland	32.6	-0.63	-0.79	0.06	0.10
United Kingdom	32.4	2.45	0.98	-0.31	1.77
Canada	32.1	0.13	-0.38	0.28	0.23
Iceland	31.5	-0.05	-0.04	-0.01	0.00
United States	30.0	-0.09	-0.08	0.00	-0.01
Australia	27.9	-1.67	-1.70	0.00	0.02
Costa Rica	27.7	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Israel	26.1	1.09	0.26	0.43	0.39
Korea	24.8	0.13	0.18	0.00	-0.05
Switzerland	23.0	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.00
Mexico	21.7	0.36	0.37	0.00	-0.01
New Zealand	20.8	0.03	0.03	0.00	0.00
Chile	7.5	0.46	0.11	-0.03	0.37
Colombia	0.0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
OECD Average	35.1	0.15	-0.01	0.01	0.15

Note: Table shows results for a single individual without children earning the average wage.

Source: OECD, 2025

While the OECD average is approximately 35.1%, this rate in Turkey stands at 40.3%, above the average (OECD, 2025). This situation indicates that the taxation of labor income is relatively heavier in Turkey and that the total fiscal burden on employees and employers is at high levels.

Turkey's position above the OECD average is primarily due to the combined effect of income tax and social security deductions. This structure reduces the net income earned by employees while also increasing labor costs for employers. Therefore, it can be said that the tax burden on labor in Turkey is more pronounced compared to many OECD countries.

Although Azerbaijan is not an OECD member, it has a lower-rate income tax structure and a different social security contribution system, resulting in a more limited overall tax burden on labor income compared to Turkey. In particular, the relatively low income tax rates and the simpler structure of the system contribute to maintaining a more balanced overall burden on labor.

When evaluated overall, OECD data clearly show that labor income in Turkey is subject to a high tax burden, while in Azerbaijan this burden is understood to be lower and more stable. This difference serves as an important indicator for comparing the impact of tax structures and social contribution systems on labor between the two countries.

Result

This study examined the tax systems of Turkey and Azerbaijan in a comparative framework in terms of the relative tax burden on labor and capital income. The findings indicate that both countries exhibit an imbalance in the distribution of the tax burden against labor income.

In Turkey, wage incomes are subject to a regular and systematic tax burden through withholding taxation mechanisms at source, while capital incomes are taxed in a relatively more flexible structure, particularly through time-based exemptions, exclusions, and differentiated taxation practices. This situation reveals that labor bears a higher tax burden compared to capital in terms of effective tax burden.

In the case of Azerbaijan, the fact that capital income is not separated in detail as a separate tax category and is evaluated within the general income tax system indicates a more integrated but less segmented tax structure. Within this structure, it is observed that labor income is taxed in a more regular and visible manner, while capital income is subject to a relatively more limited and indirect taxation regime.

When evaluated overall, it is concluded that both in Turkey and Azerbaijan, labor income is subject to a higher and more sustained tax burden compared to capital income in the tax systems. This finding has significant structural implications in terms of tax justice, income distribution, and the effectiveness of tax policy, and indicates the need to reevaluate the existing tax architecture.

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